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ARTÍCULO DE INVESTIGACIÓN

Evaluación de la reforma del sistema de protección social en el contexto de la consecución de los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible/DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8319394

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Resumen

El objetivo de este estudio es evaluar la reforma del sistema de protección social en Ucrania. Para realizar el estudio y alcanzar este objetivo, se han utilizado los métodos de investigación necesarios: abstracción, método gráfico, deducción, sistematización y generalización. Se han identificado las metas de los ODS que contribuyen a la consecución de la protección social universal, a saber: meta 1.3; meta 5.4; y meta 10.4. Además, la protección social se ha identificado como fundamental para la consecución de varios ODS, en particular: el objetivo 1.5; el objetivo 3.8; y el objetivo 8.2. El estudio constató que, según los paneles mundiales, el nivel de eficiencia de la protección social en Ucrania es del 73%. En la región europea, esta cifra es del 83,9%, lo que supone un 10,90% más que en Ucrania. El estudio concluye que el sistema de protección social en Ucrania se encuentra actualmente en una situación difícil y requiere el desarrollo de una estrategia integral de protección social para satisfacer las necesidades a largo plazo de las categorías más vulnerables de ciudadanos y alcanzar los ODS.

Palabras clave: protección social, desarrollo sostenible, categorías vulnerables de la población, estrategia de protección social.

Abstract

Assessment of the social protection system reform in the context of achieving the sustainable development goals

The purpose of this study is to assess the reform of the social protection system. To conduct the study and achieve this goal, the necessary research methods were used: abstraction, graphical method, deduction, systematization and generalization. The SDG goals that contribute to the achievement of universal social protection have been identified, namely: goal 1.3; goal 5.4; and goal 10.4. In addition, social protection has been identified as fundamental to the achievement of several SDGs, in particular: Goal 1.5; Goal 3.8 and Goal 8.2. The study found that, according to global panels, the level of efficiency of social protection in Ukraine is 73%. In the European region, this figure is 83.9%, which is 10.90% higher than in Ukraine. The study concluded that the social protection system in Ukraine is currently in a difficult state and requires the development of a comprehensive social protection strategy to meet the long-term needs of the most vulnerable categories of citizens and achieve the SDGs

Keywords: social protection, sustainable development, vulnerable categories of the population, social protection strategy.

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1.- Introduction

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, proclaimed by the United Nations (hereinafter - the UN), and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (hereinafter - the SDGs) define a list of priority development goals that are key for both developed and developing countries. These goals are aimed at eradicating poverty, protecting the entire planet, and ensuring future prosperity for all. Among the priorities agreed upon by member states, social protection is prominent, and is mentioned in the agenda as an important tool to protect all individuals and families from social hardship and market risks throughout the life cycle (UNDP, 2015). UN member states are calling for the implementation of sound national social protection systems and measures for all, including a social protection floor, to achieve significant coverage of the poor and vulnerable by 2030.

Currently, about 69.4% of the world's population lives without adequate social protection, including access to pensions, unemployment benefits, health insurance, and income security (Trifunovic, 2022). According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has at the same time "exposed deep-rooted inequalities and significant gaps in the coverage, comprehensiveness and adequacy of social protection in all countries"; and "provoked an unprecedented social protection policy response" (ILO, 2021). The time is therefore ripe to accelerate the transformation of social protection systems in light of the pandemic's heightened challenges to achieve and ensure recovery and resilience.

The ambitious goals of the 2030 Agenda and the new commitments to implementing integrated social protection systems will require concerted efforts by UN organizations and national actors, combining different activities and using new tools to find and implement more successful and effective social protection programs to achieve the 2030 goal.

This goal, given the ongoing aggressive Russian-Ukrainian war, is relevant for Ukraine today and will become critical in the recovery process, which will require a deep and comprehensive reform of the social protection system, given the growing number of vulnerable populations. In addition to the generally recognized socially vulnerable

categories of the population, the categories in need of social protection in Ukrainian society include a significant number of commissioned and wounded military personnel (who will have special needs in the future); war veterans; war veterans and persons affected by combat operations; refugees; displaced persons; and possibly even persons affected by chemical, nuclear or man-made disasters, contaminated areas, etc. The scale of the problem of growing need for social protection is currently immense and difficult to predict due to the ongoing hostilities and the uncertain nature of the overall consequences of Russian aggression. However, today Ukraine already needs to reform social protection in the perspective of the need to develop and implement effective mechanisms and instruments, not only in view of the urgency of providing social protection to needy categories of the population, but also in the light of recovery, future development as a welfare state and achievement of the SDGs by 2030. Therefore, it is important to assess the status of social protection reform in the context of the SDGs.

2.- The aim of the study

The purpose of the article is to assess the reform of the social protection system. It is advisable to carry out the assessment in the context of achieving the SDGs, which allows determining the correctness of the vector of development of the Ukrainian social protection system and its consistency with global trends, which are generally guided and shaped by the agenda 2030 and the achievement of the SDGs. For this purpose, it is advisable to

- to identify the SDGs that are significant and affect the development of social protection;
- analyze the level of social protection of the population of Ukraine in comparison with the world;
- to study the successful experience of reforming social protection to achieve the SDGs;
- to assess the reform of the Ukrainian social protection system in the context of achieving the SDGs.

3.- Analysis of recent research and publications

In recent years, the number of studies in the scientific community on social protection in the context of achieving the SDGs has been increasing. In the UNESCAP study (2018), the SDGs are defined as a tool for social protection. This is confirmed by the infographic, which clearly shows how social protection policies and systems are becoming a key element for the realization of each of the SDGs identified by the UN. In 2021, the ILO issued a report on the global status of social protection (ILO, 2021). This report presents the latest trends in social protection. The report analyzes progress in overall social protection coverage in the world, with a particular focus on achieving the SDGs. The document includes a section that explores how to build a statistical knowledge base on social protection for monitoring the relevant SDGs.

The discussion on the comprehensive framework for achieving universal social protection and its implementation as enshrined in the 2030 Agenda, especially in SDG

1, target 1.3, as well as in other international rights systems, is presented in the ILO report "Universal Social Protection: Key Concepts and International Frameworks" (ILO, 2019).

The specifics of implementing universal social protection in the context of the SDGs were studied by R. Brito. The researcher summarizes different institutional understandings of universal social protection and substantiates discussions related to the challenges of expanding social protection and the relevant implications for the SDGs (Brito, 2021).

The positive impact of social protection on reducing inequality and poverty is identified by E. Conrad, and the urgent changes needed to improve existing efforts to eradicate poverty and achieve SDG 1 are also outlined. The study notes that the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated vulnerabilities in global poverty eradication efforts that were already underway before the crisis and discusses what changes in social protection systems and policies are needed to reshape progress toward SDG 1 (Conrad, 2021).

D. Carter's study analyzes the impact of social protection and poverty alleviation on global tuberculosis incidence, using statistical modeling to link key indicators for expanding social protection coverage to tuberculosis incidence using data from the SDG Data Warehouse and the WHO's disease status database for 192 countries. This report makes the case for the impact of social protection on the health system (Carter et al, 2021).

The issue of social protection expenditures and financing for the SDGs was studied by a group of researchers led by H. Takeshima, who identified the leading role of public spending in reducing poverty and improving food and nutrition security. The study includes comparative analyses between countries. In addition, the publication examines how public spending affects social protection and other areas and how it contributes to the achievement of key SDG outcomes, especially in relation to the first and second SDGs (Takeshima et al, 2021). The specifics of financing the Social Protection Agenda of the Sustainable Development Goals are explored by Callies (2019), who presents eight financing options for creating and mobilizing resources for social protection.

The authors also highlight several publications that help to expand the analysis of the topic under study, including: Morhunov, O., Artemenko, I., Sobol, Y., Bobryshova, L., Shevchenko, S. Methodological principles of studying the essence of public administration bodies as subjects of administrative procedural law, Sobol, Y., Kondratenko, V., Okopnyk, O., Fomichov, K., Skliarenko, I. Interactions between the international convention and the system of guaranteeing the rights of persons with disabilities in Ukraine, Kondratenko, V., Manzhula, A., & Sobol, Y. The Current Factors of Ensuring the Activities of Public Administration Regarding the System of Social Adaptation of Children with Disabilities, Sobol, Y. S. Y., Myroniuk, R., Harust, Y., Myrhorod-Karpova, V. Implementation of Family Medicine in Central and Eastern Europe: Experience and Lessons for Ukraine, Nikitenko, V., Voronkova, V., Oleksenko, R., Matviienko, H., & Butkevych, O. Sustainable agricultural development paradigm formation in the context of managerial experience of industrialized countries, Nikitenko,

V., Voronkova, V., Oleksenko, R., Filoretova, L., Lanoviuk, L., Khvist, V. Perspectives of civilizational political development of world regions in the context of current challenges and opportunities.

The issue of child social protection to achieve SDG 1.3 is outlined in a joint report by the ILO and UNICEF (ILO & UNICEF, 2019). With the aim of achieving SDG 1.3, this joint report provides an overview of the state of child social protection, focusing on cash transfer programs for children and families, examining aspects such as effective coverage and financing, as well as social protection in different contexts.

The study by Nepad (2022) focuses on catalyzing integrated social protection to accelerate the achievement of the SDGs in response to the shocks of Covid-19. The study identifies how integrated social protection can be used to accelerate the achievement of the SDGs. It also focuses on the impact and good practices of the SDG Joint Fund on achieving multiple SDGs, such as SDGs 1, 5 and 10.

4.- Materials and methods

In the process of writing the article, the author used methodological tools and material that allowed to achieve the goal, primarily the following research methods:

- analysis of literary sources. This method was used to study the latest research and publications on the topic of the study and to familiarize with the main directions of development of the social protection system in the context of achieving the SDGs. The analysis of literature sources also examined the successful experience of reforming the social protection system to overcome poverty and support vulnerable groups;

- abstraction. This method made it possible to focus the study on the specifics of social protection reform, which is the subject of the article;

- graphic method. This method was used to visually improve the perception of the research results. In addition, the use of this method visually records the results of the application of systematization and generalization methods, which qualitatively enhances and facilitates the perception of the research results. Using the graphical method, 5 figures were drawn to illustrate the information presented in the article;

- the method of deduction. This method helped to logically separate the current directions of development of the social protection system in accordance with the goals of the SDGs;

- methods of systematization and generalization. These methods were used to evaluate the reform of the social protection system and to generalize the research in writing the conclusions.

The article was based on scientific articles and publications, UN materials, materials of the International Labor Organization, ILO World Social Protection Data Dashboards, the Global SDG Indicators Data Platform of the UN Statistics, etc.

5.- Results of the study

The 17 SDGs represent an ambitious and comprehensive global plan for sustainable development until 2030, reflecting a set of global aspirations for the development of people, planet and long-term prosperity in different countries and regions (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Global goals of the SDGs (UNDO, 2015)

Source: Authors development

It is a comprehensive plan that includes the most significant areas and defines important results to be achieved in each area to ensure sustainable development of the planet and humanity. These goals include: fighting poverty and hunger; improving public health and access to quality education; ensuring gender equality; ensuring access to water and adequate sanitation; promoting the use of renewable energy sources; striving for decent working conditions and economic growth; developing innovation and

infrastructure; reducing inequality in all its manifestations; ensuring sustainable development of cities and communities; implementing principles and conditions for sustainable consumption; effective means of combating climate change; and ensuring the protection of human rights.

Achieving universal social protection is consistent with the 2030 Agenda, especially with Target 1.3 "Establish nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including a social protection floor, and achieve significant coverage of the poor and vulnerable by 2030" SDG 1 (End poverty in all its forms worldwide). In addition to SDG 1, social protection is explicitly mentioned as a key instrument for achieving SDG 5 (Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls), target 5.4 "Recognize and value unpaid care and domestic work through public services, infrastructure and social protection policies, and promote shared responsibility within the household and family, in accordance with national contexts and SDG 10 (Reduce inequality), target 10.4 "Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality".

In addition, social protection is considered fundamental to the achievement of several SDGs, including:

- Goal 1.5. "By 2030, build the resilience of the poor and vulnerable, and reduce their impacts and vulnerabilities to climate change extremes and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters."

- SDG 3 (Promote good health through healthy lives and well-being for all at all ages), target 3.8 "Achieve universal health coverage, including financial protection, access to quality essential health services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all";

- SDG 8 (Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all), target 8.2 "Develop and implement a global youth employment strategy and implement the ILO Global Jobs Pact" (Brito, 2022).

It should be noted that in the context of the global pandemic, the number of joint programs aimed at social protection has significantly increased as a response to the shocks caused by the crisis. Initially, the focus was on natural disasters and the impact of climate change (and hence contributions to the relevant SDGs related to them), but then expanded to mitigate the broader socio-economic impact of the health crisis. As the scope and scale of vulnerability has rapidly increased, the importance of social protection, in particular those systems that require greater sensitivity and adaptation, has come to the fore and led to strategic adjustments across all joint programs (Nepad, 2022).

According to the ILO's Global Social Protection Coverage Report, the vast majority of children worldwide still lack effective social protection - only one in four children (26.4

percent) receives social assistance. Only 45 percent of women with newborns worldwide receive cash maternity benefits. Only one in three people with severe disabilities (33.5 percent) worldwide receives disability benefits. Coverage of unemployment benefits is even lower; only 18.6 percent of the unemployed globally are effectively covered. And while 77.5 percent of people over retirement age receive some form of old-age pension, large disparities remain between regions, between rural and urban areas, and between women and men (ILO, 2021).

Public spending on social protection also varies significantly. On average, countries spend 12.8 percent of their gross domestic product (GDP) on social protection (excluding health care), but high-income countries spend 16.4 percent and low-income countries spend only 1.1 percent of their GDP on social protection. The financing gap (the additional spending needed to provide at least a social protection floor for all) has increased by about 30 percent since the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis. According to the ILO, to guarantee at least basic social protection coverage, low-income countries will need to invest an additional US\$77.9 billion per year, lower-middle-income countries an additional US\$362.9 billion per year, and upper-middle-income countries an additional US\$750.8 billion per year. This is equivalent to 15.9, 5.1, and 3.1 percent of their GDP, respectively (ILO, 2021).

Access to at least a basic level of social security throughout the life cycle is a human right, fundamental to human health and dignity. Social protection systems are at the heart of efforts to ensure decent living conditions for all people throughout their lives. The proportion of the population covered by the minimum levels of social protection indicates the extent to which the ideal of social protection universality has been achieved and how safe the living conditions and health of the population are. Therefore, it is a key indicator that conveys information about how well the population is protected from various unforeseen situations that can potentially be encountered in life. To analyze the situation, the World Social Protection Dashboards were created (ILO, 2020).

According to the World Social Protection Dashboards, the level of social protection efficiency in the world is 46.9%, while in Ukraine it is 73% (Fig. 2).

Compared to the global level, Ukraine has a high level of social protection coverage. At the same time, in the European region, this figure is 83.9%, which is 10.90% higher than in Ukraine. However, it should be noted that the European region generally has the highest level of effective social coverage of all regions.

Figure 2. The level of efficiency of social protection in Ukraine compared to the global level (ILO, 2021)

Source: Authors development

Figure 3. Social protection performance in Ukraine compared to the global and regional levels by categories of people (ILO, 2021)

Source: Authors development

It should be noted that Ukraine has a low level of population coverage by pension schemes compared to the world and the European region. At the same time, the strengths of Ukraine's social protection system include support for children and mothers, the unemployed, and people with disabilities. Ukraine has made significant progress in social protection of these categories.

The next indicator to be analyzed is the level of social protection expenditures as a percentage of GDP (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Level of social protection expenditures, % of GDP (ILO, 2021)

Source: Authors development

Thus, while the global average for social protection expenditures is 12.9% of GDP, in European countries this figure reaches 17.4%. Ukraine occupies an intermediate position with a level of social protection expenditures of 16.2% of GDP.

The success of European countries in providing social protection is justified by the European Consensus on Development, which enshrines the obligation of both the EU and its member states to promote "adequate and sustainable social protection." Therefore, the EU supports a basic level of social protection as a right for all, and especially for children, vulnerable people of working age and the elderly. The main obstacle to building effective social protection systems is the lack of allocated resources. Therefore, the EU supports economic transformation and policies that mobilize resources, especially from domestic sources, to generate stable and sufficient revenues for social protection (Social protection, n.d.).

At the same time, the EU has a specialized European Union Social Protection System (EU-SPS) Program, which is an action of the European Union funded by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The OECD Development Centre and the Finnish Government's National Institute of Health and Welfare (THL) manage the program, under which EU-SPS supports low- and middle-income countries in building sustainable and inclusive social protection systems. The program was implemented over four and a half years until April 2019 in partnership with national and regional social protection authorities, think tanks and expert institutions in 10 countries. The program had three specific objectives:

- 1) to develop appropriate methodologies and tools;
- 2) to increase administrative and technical capacity;
- 3) generate evidence-based knowledge for future cooperation with the EU and for use by other development partners on the effectiveness of social protection in reducing poverty and vulnerability, addressing inequalities, and promoting social cohesion (OECD, 2019).

The program's findings have shown that a number of national social protection strategies adopted around the world in recent years have driven the implementation of integrated systems used by many different countries. The strategies provide a framework for comprehensive and integrated approaches that create synergies across sectors, improving impact and value for money. And such integrated systems increase efficiency and provide opportunities for development multipliers. Expenditure sector plans provide operational guidance for moving from strategy to implementation. Lessons learned and good practices over the past decade from this program identify a number of important opportunities for development partners to improve the efficiency and value for money of their social protection support, namely the formulation of national social protection strategies. Expenditure sector plans provide a bridge from abstract strategies to actual implementation. They allow governments to translate the long-term visions contained in national strategies into medium-term action plans with specific programs, realistic budgets, and actionable timelines (OECD, 2019). Thus, for the effective implementation of the social protection system, it is necessary to formulate a strategic vision and develop relevant national strategies that create the basis for further planning and target setting.

Social protection reform in Ukraine has been ongoing since the country's independence. With the start of the decentralization reform, social protection reform has acquired new dimensions and identified new problematic sectors that require immediate response from the competent authorities. Despite the large number of legal acts adopted in the field of social protection over the 30 years of our country's independence, a wide range of issues and problems remain unresolved at the legislative level.

Ukraine's social protection system includes a wide range of social assistance, insurance, benefits, and subsidies, covering approximately 19-22 million people in the country. The national social protection programs have recently been expanded and continue to adapt through horizontal (for IDPs, etc.) and vertical expansion (for pensions, etc.), as well as through emergency and response assistance to internal displacement during the conflict in Donetsk and Luhansk oblasts and the annexation of Crimea in 2014, to revenue losses from the COVID-19 pandemic, and to the significant increase in humanitarian needs during the current escalation of the Russia-Ukraine war. Despite continued government spending on social protection systems, growing needs outpaced the coverage and adequacy of social benefits even before the current phase of the war. In particular, national social protection programs and social transfers need to:

- 1) further expanding coverage to ensure that people who are eligible for state support can actually receive it, especially in times of war,
- 2) increasing the adequacy of cash transfers of existing social benefits to ensure that they are sufficient to enable people to meet their basic needs in the current context,
- 3) increasing resources and financial investments to meet needs during current and future crises (Beyko & Lacerda, 2023).

Following the Russian invasion in early 2022, the World Bank, the Government of Ukraine, and the European Commission estimated and reported that the social protection and livelihoods sector suffered losses of US\$50.6 billion, mainly related to job losses, reduced household wage income, increased poverty, and reduced access to basic needs, including energy and food (World Bank, 2022).

Using the global platform of SDG indicators of UN Statistics, we will assess the reform of the social protection system in the context of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. To do this, we will use the platform to analyze the status of the following goals, which are key to the development of social protection:

1) Goal 1.3. "Introduce nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including a social protection floor, and achieve significant coverage of the poor and vulnerable by 2030". This is the main goal for which the state, as a social protection agent, must take concrete steps:

- Establishment of national joint groups of social protection floors;
- Supporting national dialogues;
- Conducting joint assessments;
- Integrate social protection systems, including the social protection floor, into national development plans and develop/improve social protection schemes;
- Building national statistical capacity (UN, 2015);

2) target 1.5. "By 2030, increase the resilience of the poor and vulnerable, and reduce their exposure and vulnerability to climate change extremes and other economic, social and environmental shocks and disasters";

3) target 3.8. "Achieve universal health coverage, including protection against financial risks, access to quality essential health services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all";

4) Objective 5.4. "Recognize and value unpaid care and domestic work through public services, infrastructure and social protection policies, and promote shared responsibility within the household and family, in accordance with national contexts;

5) Target 8.2. "Develop and implement a global youth employment strategy and implement the ILO Global Jobs Pact";

6) target 10.4. "Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and gradually achieve greater equality".

In Fig. 5, we will determine the state of implementation of the above SDGs by Ukraine according to the global platform of SDG indicators of the UN statistics.

Figure 5. Status of SDG implementation in terms of social protection reform in Ukraine

Source: Authors development

The only target in terms of social protection implementation that has been achieved is target 1.5 on increasing the resilience of the poor and vulnerable. Therefore, in general, we can assess the effectiveness of social protection reform as unsatisfactory. Since 2015, the country has not developed a Strategy for the Development of the Social Protection System and, accordingly, its implementation plan.

Similar conclusions were reached by the IMF monitoring program, which recommends reforming the social protection system to meet the needs of IDPs and war veterans. Currently, a vision of approaches to reforming the social protection system is being developed to ensure targeted, sufficient and effective social assistance to the population, taking into account the needs of these new categories (Interfax-Ukraine, 2022).

6. Conclusions

Ukraine's social protection system is currently in a difficult situation due to the increased burden of expanding the categories of people in need of protection and the lack of funding in the context of an overall budget deficit due to the shrinking economy and the need to finance defense needs. The ongoing war has exacerbated the disadvantaged situation of children, women, the elderly, and people with disabilities. Many in these groups were already extremely vulnerable before the war. As millions of Ukrainians now face war, displacement and poverty, social support must be targeted and controlled, given Ukraine's limited financial resources. Today, neither the Ukrainian government nor international financial institutions have a clear understanding of the scale of public spending on social assistance, which makes it urgently financially necessary for Ukraine to move to a narrower model of state support for vulnerable groups. This could significantly reduce the level of state aid in the long run as a result of further reform of the social protection system.

While the current challenges require immediate action, Ukraine needs a comprehensive social protection strategy to address the long-term needs of its most vulnerable citizens and achieve the SDGs. Significant medium- and long-term employment challenges and social priorities that existed before the invasion must also be addressed in the context of the war and the upcoming recovery.

The Ukrainian government continues to pursue wide-ranging reforms of the social security system as the country faces the ever-increasing costs of the war with Russia, which is now in its second year. And the context of further reforms should be correlated with the need to implement the 2030 Agenda in terms of achieving the SDGs. In accordance with the IMF's recommendations and with the active assistance of the Fund's experts, Ukraine is now starting to work on its own national social protection development strategy, which will allow to elaborate a general vision of the development of the social sphere and support and determine the priorities for the development of social protection for the categories of the population in need. Cooperation with the IRF will help integrate the social protection system into national development plans and improve existing social assistance schemes. This, in turn, will help to achieve SDG 1.3 "Establish nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures for all, including a social protection floor, and achieve universal coverage of the poor and vulnerable by 2030", which will form the necessary basis for achieving the following goals that will promote social protection for vulnerable groups and are dependent on its development (primarily SDGs: 3.8, 5.4, 8.2, 10.4).

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